

REDUCING DISRUPTIVE BEHAVIOR AMONG SPECIAL EDUCATION NEEDS CHILDREN OF 3 BELLATRIX THROUGH THE *INDAHNYA SOLAT* ACTIVITY

^aHazzizul Firdaus Bin Hodari

^bNor Huda Binti Tumi'an

^cMarshella Binti Manshor

^dMohd Rafizal Bin A Rahman

^{abcd}*Sekolah Kebangsaan Lembah Beringin, Malaysia*

^a*hfzulziezul17@gmail.com*

^b*norpetunjuk75@gmail.com*

^c*g-30336774@moe-dl.edu.my*

^d*g-91336780@moe-dl.edu.my*

ABSTRACT

Indahnya Solat (Beautiful Prayer) is the best practice of behavior management for Students with Special Education Needs (SEN) learning problems implemented in the Special Education Integration Program Year 3 class involving 6 students in a school in Hulu Selangor. The purpose of this study as a way to educate SEN learning problems that often disagree, often fight, make too much noise, extreme movement and disturb peers in the classroom. Based on observations, such disruptive behaviors result in students being less focused and disrupt teaching and learning sessions. Therefore, this activity is expected to provide awareness and gentleness to SEN of the learning problems involved. It can also strengthen the practice of performing obligatory prayers 5 times a day at home. In line with the Malaysian National Education Philosophy, this activity is an effort to provide students who are balanced and harmonious in terms of intellectual, spiritual, emotional and physical. Qualitative methods were used for data collection and analysis through observations, interviews and document analysis. Findings from this study, found that 4 out of 6 SEN people with learning difficulties showed an increase in positive behaviors. The conclusion from this study, there are some improvements that need to be implemented to improve the student's potential as a continuation of the activity *Indahnya Solat* in order to bring better results and effects. Among them are the mentee mentor program, collaborative with Islamic Education subjects, *Bestari Solat* Camp and Implementation of *Dhuha* Prayer Activities

Keywords: Prayer, behavior management, disruptive behavior, Special Education Needs (SEN), Special Education Program Integration

1. Introduction

Disruptive behaviours are behaviour such as hyperactivity, extreme changes, noise, unnecessary student movements, disturbing classmates, loud laughter and physically aggressive behaviours such as pushing or punching in class. Kerr & Nelson (1998) state that; destructive behaviour is any behaviour that interferes with the learning process that is taking place in the classroom, including those that aim to gain attention, whether positively or negatively. In the context of school education, disruptive behavioural can affect the smooth running of the teaching and learning process in the classroom. Hymn is a prayer and a link between man and his Creator. Through prayer they can achieve peace of mind, purify the heart, form a good personality and then encourage individuals to do good deeds and prevent from committing evil.

The words of Allah from Surah Al-Ankabut, verse 45 which means:

“Read what has been revealed to you, namely Al-Kitab (Al-Quran) and establish prayer. Indeed, the prayer prevents (deeds) of abomination and evil. And indeed, the remembrance of Allah (salat) is greater (superiority than other acts of worship). And Allah knows what you do. ”

In this regard, Islam commands to teach, guide and emphasize the implementation of obligatory prayers as a practice of their children as early as 7 years old. Islam has also recommended beating as early as seven years old if they still miss the five daily prayers (as to educate).

Recognizing the fact those SEN pupils with learning problems in our school possessing disruptive behaviour, hence the practice of prayer is applied. The first approach is to perform the dawn prayer after attending school and it has been practiced since early 2020. This practice is continued in schools for children who fail to fulfil the responsibility of prayer at home. The implementation of the activity aims to help cleanse the heart from the rough soul, one of the spiritual fillings, further emphasizing the importance of performing prayers as an obligation of Muslims.

It is in line with the objectives of the National Education Philosophy written in 1987 which is stated as follows: “Education in Malaysia is a continuous effort towards further developing the potential of individuals in a comprehensive and integrated manner to create a balanced and harmonious human being intellectually, spiritually, emotionally and physical based on faith and obedience to God. This effort is to produce Malaysians who are knowledgeable, skilled, virtuous, and responsible. In this regard, to achieve the goal of producing pious or perfect human beings, among the policy matters that need to be prioritized is to develop a noble personality through the implementation of five times prayers on each SEN pupils with learning problem.

2. Problem Statement

This study was conducted to evaluate the behavioral changes of SEN pupils with learning problems in our school by controlling their disruptive behavior in the classroom in the new norm era Covid-19. The study samples were 6 SEN pupils with learning problems in our school. Qualitative methods were used for data collection and analysis through observations, interviews and document analysis.

Issues related to SEN pupils’ behavioral problems are clearly visible when they behave destructively, often neglect attending school and are not interested in doing the learning

assignments given. This has caused SEN teachers to design and implement this study in hope that there will be a change in attitude and the learning process can run smoothly.

2.1 Research Questions

- a. Is performing the 5 times prayers able to change attitudes and learning problems in SEN classroom?
- b. What positive attitude can be applied among SEN pupils if performing the obligatory prayers 5 times?

2.2 Research Objectives

- a. To strengthen self-discipline and thus performing the obligatory 5 times prayer.
- b. To educate and apply pure values in the context of Special Education Needs pupils.

2.3 Target Groups

This study involved 6 SEN pupils with learning problems. They consisted of:

Table 1 Study findings of the student's disruptive behavior

No.	Sample	Disruptive Behavior	Observation	Interview
1	Sample 1	Disturbing	/	-
2	Sample 2	Manipulation	/	/
3	Sample 3	Anger management	/	/
4	Sample 4	Anger management and sulky	/	/
5	Sample 5	Activeness and disturbing	/	-
6	Sample 6	Extreme passiveness	/	-

2.4 Justification of the Study

This study was conducted on SEN pupils with learning problems whereas some of them were not directly involved in this study. This is due to the fact that two of them are new comers in 2021, which cannot be detected from the aspect of behavioural changes. The students in question are Sample 5 and Sample 6. Meanwhile, Sample 1 was not involved in the interview session because he is a Down Syndrome child who is not fluent in speaking.

3. Literature Review

Thalib, M. (1997), stated that, prayer education is a form of early education that should be emphasized as a practice of children as early as seven years old as recommended by the Prophet SAW. This is because prayer is a pillar of religion that must be performed by every Muslim. It is an important identity that distinguishes between Muslims and non-Muslims. Parents in particular need to be aware of their responsibility to ensure that children perform prayers consistently because prayer is the main pillar to fill the souls of children with monotheistic beliefs (Thalib, 1997).

Furthermore, Nik Zaiton, M., N. (2007), stated that from the studies that have been made on the inculcation of noble morals in general is depending on the practice of quality prayer. Only a perfect prayer will guarantee the integrity of one's morals as well as be an

invulnerable shield and fortress in the face of slander, evil, wickedness and satanic incitement (Nik Zaiton, 2007). This study can be further strengthened based on the statement from Siti Rokiah, A. G. (2007), in his study entitled "Prayer Practice Among Students: A Study at the Center for Instructor Training and Advanced Skills (CIAST), Shah Alam" found that there is a significant relation between the degree of prayer practice with the level of student morality (Siti Rokiah, 2007).

Through the findings of Fariyah, H. (2006) proved that the neglect of obligatory prayers is one of the factors in the occurrence of symptoms of moral decay among youth in today's society. Therefore, it is appropriate to practice prayer among children to coincide with the title of the study 'Reducing disruptive behaviour among Special Education Needs children of 3 Bellatrix through the activity *Indahnya Solat*.

4. Research Methodology

This study uses research methodology such as observations conducted in the classroom, interviews with SEN pupils with learning problems and analysis of source documents from the *Analisis Pengkalan Data Murid (APDM)* attendance system.

4.1 Checklist

After conducting this study there were positive attitude changes among SEN pupils with learning problems. Changes in student attitudes were observed and all data were recorded through constructed checklists and observations. All four samples have undergone significant changes. Before the 'best practice activity' was carried out, Sample 4 was often sullen and hot-tempered. As the result, changes in positive attitudes become increasingly apparent. Sample 4 is calm in talking with friends and teachers.

The angry attitude that was often seen before subsided from day to day. From the aspect of socializing and speaking, he (the subject) became more polite and did not use neither abusive words nor cursing. Apart from that, Sample 1 has been listening to the teacher's instructions better. Meanwhile, Sample 2 is now easy to forgive the mistakes of his friends. This best practice has clearly changed the attitude of SEN students in a more positive direction.

Table 2 Sample of student's positive development

No. Sample	Names	Positive development
1	Sample 1	Concentrate and do homework
2	Sample 2	Listen to the teacher's instructions
3	Sample 3	Becomes forgiving
4	Sample 4	Less sulking and diligent in helping teachers

4.2 Interview

Based on the interview session with several respondents, it was found that prayer activities can give a better understanding on the responsibilities as a Muslim student. This is based on several questions related to prayer and SEN pupils' interest in learning problems in school. All SEN pupils with learning difficulties showed love and interest in school and were able to take

good care of their personalities. Significant changes occurred to Sample 1 who used to influence students, fighting and hating to do school work but nowadays he turned to be helpful to other friends.

4.3 Level of Attendance in Analisis Pangkalan Data Murid (Apdm) System

The percentage of SEN pupils' attendance has increased; teaching progress is getting better. A responsible attitude and love for school prevails among them. All attendance data is taken in the student APDM system. Before the *Indahnya Solat* program was practiced, the attendance percentage was not encouraging in January 2020 which was 89.5 %, but after this best practice was implemented, the attendance percentage of the entire SEN classroom has increased by 3.4 % to 92.9 % in September 2020. This best practice is able to discipline students and cultivate an attitude of love for school because they feel safer and the prayer activities have successfully changed their behaviour and bring them closer to spirituality. The 100% attendance percentage can be seen in the presence of Sample 1 and Sample 3.

Table 3 Percentage of attendance based on months

No.	Months	% Attendance
1	January 2020	89.5%
2	September 2020	92.9%

4.4 Student Work Results

After disciplining students by performing obligatory prayers 5 times, pupils are increasingly showing interest in learning as well as helping weaker friends. Data is obtained by looking at the results of students' work that is getting neater and better. For example, Sample 1 and Sample 2 previously were neglecting to do schoolwork and liked to play in class, yet after this best practice was practiced, they showed a very noticeable change. Now the results of their assignments are neater and they are able to do assignments without the full guidance of the teacher. Apart from that, there is also healthy competition among them in completing all teacher assignments. The researcher placed some of the student's work on the appendix included in this study.

5. Study Reflection/Discussion

Findings of the study showed that *Indahnya Solat* activities have improved students' discipline in terms of behaviour and increasing the percentage of attendance to school. Pupils are increasingly fond of going to school and studying together. The aspect of attendance is very important in the efforts of teachers to educate and form successful human capital of the world and the hereafter.

Apart from that, these best practices have also helped teachers in the management of students in the classroom. For example, students are diligent in completing any assignment even if it is not completely 'complete'. The attitude of volunteering in helping friends also exists among them without being told by the teacher. This pure effort clearly indicates the occurrence of positive behavioural changes and shaping their social skills. This best practice should be practiced not only at SEN pupils, but throughout the primary level as a whole. The approach towards spirituality is indeed very helpful in shaping personality of whom to become a superior student.

6. Proposed Future Studies

The best practice of *Indahnya Solat* has positive impact on SEN pupils. Among other studies in the formation of student behaviour that can be carried out are the Mentor Mentee (Mentor and Prodigy) program among SEN pupils, teaching prayer collaboratively with the subject of Islamic Education, Smart Prayer Camp and Implementation of *Dhuha* (post dawn prayer) Prayer Activities with students. This study can also be done with mainstream and preschool students. This noble practice should be carried out continuously in shaping the personality of the student.

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Appendices

Appendix 1

Observation Form Reducing Disruptive Behavior
 Sample 1.

Borang pemerhatian mengurangkan tingkah laku Diskruptif MBK PPKI 3 Bellatrix
 SKLB

Nama : _____

BIL	KETERANGAN TINGKAH LAKU	CATATAN									
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
	Kelakuan Negatif										
1.	Merosakkan harta benda sendiri /orang lain	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓
2.	Cepat berkelahi/bertindak	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓
3.	Cepat marah/meradang										
4.	Mengacau/menguasai orang lain	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓
5.	Mencederakan orang lain										
6.	Panas baran										
7.	Perlakuan negatif berlaku tiba-tiba										
	Kelakuan positif										
1.	Menghormati rakan dan guru	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓
2.	Mendengar arahan guru dan rakan	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
3.	Bertolak ansur				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
4.	Membantu rakan dan guru			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
5.	Menyiapkan kerja sekolah				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
6.	Mudah memaafkan	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
7.	Bertutur dengan sopan				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Sample 2.

Borang pemerhatian mengurangkan tingkah laku Diskruptif MBK PPKI 3 Bellatrix
 SKLB

Nama: _____

BIL	KETERANGAN TINGKAH LAKU	CATATAN									
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
	Kelakuan Negatif										
1.	Merosakkan harta benda sendiri /orang lain										
2.	Cepat berkelahi/bertindak	✓✓ ✓✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓	✓	✓				
3.	Cepat marah/meradang	✓ ✓	✓	✓	✓	✓					
4.	Mengacau/menguasai orang lain	✓✓ ✓✓	✓✓ ✓✓	✓✓ ✓✓	✓✓ ✓✓	✓✓ ✓✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓
5.	Mencederakan orang lain										
6.	Panas baran										
7.	Perlakuan negatif berlaku tiba-tiba										
	Kelakuan positif										
1.	Menghormati rakan dan guru	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓
2.	Mendengar arahan guru dan rakan	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓
3.	Bertolak ansur					✓	✓	✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓
4.	Membantu rakan dan guru	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓
5.	Menyiapkan kerja sekolah	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓
6.	Mudah memaafkan						✓	✓	✓	✓✓	✓✓
7.	Bertutur dengan sopan				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓

Sample 3.

Borang pemerhatian mengurangkan tingkah laku Diskruptif MBK PPKI 3 Bellatrix
SKLB

Nama : _____ 1961

BIL	KETERANGAN TINGKAH LAKU	CATATAN									
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
	Kelakuan Negatif										
1.	Merosakkan harta benda sendiri /orang lain										
2.	Cepat berkelahi/bertindak	✓✓ ✓✓	✓✓ ✓✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓
3.	Cepat marah/meradang	✓✓ ✓✓	✓✓ ✓✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓
4.	Mengacau/menguasai orang lain										
5.	Mencederakan orang lain										
6.	Panas baran	✓✓ ✓✓	✓✓ ✓✓	✓✓ ✓✓	✓ ✓						
7.	Perlakuan negatif berlaku tiba-tiba										
	Kelakuan positif										
1.	Menghormati rakan dan guru	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓
2.	Mendengar arahan guru dan rakan	✓	✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓
3.	Bertolak ansur					✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
4.	Membantu rakan dan guru	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓
5.	Menyiapkan kerja sekolah	✓	✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓
6.	Mudah memaafkan			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
7.	Bertutur dengan sopan	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓ ✓

Sample 4.

Borang pemerhatian mengurangkan tingkah laku Diskruptif MBK PPKI 3 Bellatrix
 SKLB

Nama : _____

BIL	KETERANGAN TINGKAH LAKU	CATATAN									
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
	Kelakuan Negatif										
1.	Merosakkan harta benda sendiri /orang lain	✓									
2.	Cepat berkelahi/bertindak	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓
3.	Cepat marah/meradang	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓
4.	Mengacau/menguasai orang lain	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓
5.	Mencederakan orang lain										
6.	Panas baran	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓
7.	Perlakuan negatif berlaku tiba-tiba										
	Kelakuan positif										
1.	Menghormati rakan dan guru	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
2.	Mendengar arahan guru dan rakan	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
3.	Bertolak ansur						✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
4.	Membantu rakan dan guru			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
5.	Menyiapkan kerja sekolah	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
6.	Mudah memaafkan						✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
7.	Bertutur dengan sopan	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

APPENDIX 2.

Interview Questions

No.	Interview Questions of <i>Indahnya Solat</i> activity.
1	<i>Adakah kamu suka belajar di dalam kelas ini?</i>
2	<i>Apakah perkara yang kamu tidak suka semasa belajar di kelas ini?</i>
3	<i>Sebagai umat Islam berapa kali solat fardhu dalam sehari?</i>
4	<i>Adakah kamu pernah melihat orang bersolat dan membaca ayat-ayat bacaan dalam solat?</i>
5	<i>Adakah kamu suka membuat aktiviti pembelajaran di dalam kelas seperti menulis dan mewarna?</i>
6	<i>Adakah hasil tugas kamu cantik dan kemas?</i>

Findings of Interview Session Before *Indahnya Solat* Activity

No.	Interview Questions of <i>Indahnya Solat</i> Activity	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4
1	<i>Adakah kamu suka belajar di dalam kelas ini?</i>	<i>Tak suka sangat</i>	<i>Biasa sahaja</i>	<i>Suka</i>
2	<i>Apakah perkara yang kamu tidak suka semasa belajar di kelas ini?</i>	<i>Banyak kerja</i>	<i>Kawan bising</i>	<i>Kawan kacau</i>
3	<i>Sebagai umat Islam berapa kali solat fardhu dalam sehari?</i>	<i>Tak tahu</i>	<i>Emmm tiga</i>	<i>Lima kali</i>
4	<i>Adakah kamu pernah melihat orang bersolat dan membaca ayat-ayat bacaan dalam solat?</i>	<i>Pernah</i>	<i>Pernah</i>	<i>Pernah</i>
5	<i>Adakah kamu suka membuat aktiviti pembelajaran di dalam kelas seperti menulis dan mewarna?</i>	<i>Suka sikit</i>	<i>Tak suka</i>	<i>Suka</i>
6	<i>Adakah hasil tugas kamu cantik dan kemas?</i>	<i>Tak cantik</i>	<i>Tak cantik</i>	<i>Cantik sikit</i>

Findings of Interview Session After *Indahnya Solat* Activity

Bil	Interview Questions of <i>Indahnya Solat</i> Activity	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4
1	Adakah kamu suka belajar di dalam kelas ini?	Suka	Emm suka	Suka
2	Apakah perkara yang kamu tidak suka semasa belajar di kelas ini?	Tak tau	Suka.. Eh apa dia? Tak ada	Tak ada
3	Sebagai umat Islam berapa kali solat fardhu dalam sehari?	Lima	Lima waktu	Lima
4	Adakah kamu pernah melihat orang bersolat dan membaca ayat-ayat bacaan dalam solat?	Pernah. Di surau	Tak, tak pernah. Eh pernah. Kat masjid	Pernah. Di surau
5	Adakah kamu suka membuat aktiviti pembelajaran di dalam kelas seperti menulis dan mewarna?	Suka	Suka	Suka
6	Adakah hasil tugasan kamu cantik dan kemas?	Emm cantik	Emm kemas	Cantik sikit-sikit

APPENDIX 3. Level of Attendance (APDM)

Maklumat Murid Bukan Warga	Laporan Kedatangan Murid																															Jum. Hari Sekolah	Jum. Hadir (B)	% Hadir (A)																					
	Tahun	Kelas	Papar	Bulan	Hari																																																		
Kehadiran Subjek e-Rekod Kesihatan Murid (eRKM) Laporan > Kemudahan v Tukar Katalaluan eHelpdesk 0 aduan baru Utiliti v Laman Utama Muat Turun > Log Keluar	2020	KHAS PPKI	Papar	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	19	68/76	89.5%																		
	January	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	3/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	2/4	3/4	3/4	3/4	3/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	3/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	19	68/76	89.5%																			
	February	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	19	71/76	93.4%																			
	March	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	10	33/40	82.5%																			
	April	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	0	0/0	0.0%																			
	May	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	0	0/0	0.0%																			
	June	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	5	0/0	0.0%																			
	July	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	21	37/44	84.1%																			
	August	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	0	58/64	90.6%																			
	September	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	21	78/84	92.9%																			
	October	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	9	30/36	83.3%																			
	November	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	0	0/0	0.0%																			
December	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	0	0/0	0.0%																				
				Cuti Sabtu dan Ahad																															Cuti Umum			Cuti Negeri			Cuti Penggal			Cuti Sekolah/Peristiwa			Hari Ganti Sekolah								
				Masa capaian= 4.2787 saat																																																			

APPENDIX 4.

Students Work Results.
 Results from January 2020.

Results from February 2020.

Results from March 2020.

lain

4. Bulatkan objek ikut nombor.

a. **4** b. **6** c. **5**

5. Bilang manik. Warnakan nombornya.

a. **6** 4 5

b. 6 5 **4**

c. 4 6 **5**

212
221
Buku teks halaman 12

Susun Nombor **Aktiviti 2**

1. Padankan nombor secara menaik.

2. Lengkapkan.

a.

2	3	4	5	6	7
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b.

4	5	6	7	8	9	10
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c.

6	7	8	9	10
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3. Susun nombor secara menaik.

a.

2	3	4	5
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b.

6	7	8	9	10
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212
226
**Bantuan guru*